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Abstract

This paper investigates the impact of the Ebola epidemic on foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittance inflows across 28 African countries between 2000 and 2019. While existing literature highlights the economic costs of epidemics within affected countries, limited attention has been given to the broader financial repercussions—particularly on external financial flows and regional spillovers. This study addresses this gap by examining the dynamic responses of FDI and remittances to Ebola outbreaks using a local projection method (LPM) and validating the findings through system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to address endogeneity concerns. We construct a unique Ebola shock variable that captures both direct and indirect exposure, allowing for comparative analysis across affected countries, neighboring countries, and the broader region. The results reveal a sharp and persistent decline in FDI following Ebola outbreaks, especially in directly affected countries, driven by heightened uncertainty and investor risk aversion. In contrast, remittance inflows exhibit a counter-cyclical pattern, rising significantly in affected countries as diaspora communities respond to increased financial needs. Spillover effects are also evident: neighboring countries experience FDI losses but weaker remittance responses.

JEL Codes: I18; F21; F24; F22

Keywords: Epidemic shocks; Foreign direct investment (FDI); Remittances; Migration

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1 Introduction

In March 2014, "*Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) sounded an alarm: They were struggling to contain an outbreak of Ebola in Guinea*" [The Economist, 2018]. Between December 2013 and January 2016, the Ebola epidemic spread across several Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries, with a particularly high concentration of cases in West Africa. Guinea, Liberia, Sierra Leone, and to a lesser extent Nigeria, were particularly affected. Individual health expenditures are particularly low in SSA. This has an impact on macroeconomic fundamental aggregates such as employment, growth, or inflation. [The Economist, 2014]. As for the macroeconomic outlook, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and remittances are two critical sources of capital that support growth, development, and resilience. The outbreak of a major epidemic can disrupt investor confidence, distort labor mobility, and weaken economic fundamentals—leading to sharp declines in FDI inflows. At the same time, these crises can trigger increased remittance flows as diaspora communities seek to support affected households, acting as a form of informal insurance.

Recent literature has increasingly examined the economic consequences of health shocks, with a focus on how infectious diseases affect both macroeconomic indicators and external financial flows. Compared to non-communicable diseases, epidemics of infectious diseases generate more immediate and severe economic disruptions, often through heightened uncertainty and behavioral responses such as panic or reduced mobility (Bish and Michie [2010]; Bloom et al. [1998]; Bloom et al. [2014]; Bloom et al. [2019]; Hassan et al. [2023]). FDI, in particular, is sensitive to such risks. Ghosh and Renna [2015] found that communicable diseases substantially reduce FDI inflows across 114 countries, while Furceri et al. [2021] examined past pandemics such as SARS, H1N1, and Ebola, showing that they led to significant declines in investment, employment, and GDP in affected countries. Similarly, Jordà et al. [2022] analyzed major pandemics over the past century and found that these shocks are typically followed by sustained periods of depressed economic activity and lower real interest rates, partly due to reduced investor confidence. Cavallo et al. [2013] investigated the economic effects of epidemics and natural disasters, concluding that epidemics tend to produce more persistent effects on capital flows than many natural shocks.

In contrast, remittances tend to behave counter-cyclically. They often increase during periods of crisis, as migrants send more money home to help families cope with adverse conditions. Several studies confirm this trend. Mohapatra et al. [2012] found that international remittances tend to rise after natural disasters, helping to bolster household resilience. Beuermann and McKelvey [2016] highlighted the capacity of remittances to offset the negative economic effects of health shocks, particularly when households lack access to private insurance. Ponce et al. [2011] documented the positive impact of remittances on health behaviors in Ecuador, including increased vaccination and health-related expenditures. Even during health crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, remittances have remained resilient or increased in some regions, reflecting their importance as a social

safety net (Shastri and Garg [2022]; Chami et al. [2005]).

Despite the growing body of research examining the economic impacts of epidemic shocks—such as Ebola, SARS, and COVID-19—most existing studies have focused primarily on the direct effects within countries that experienced major outbreaks. While these works have provided valuable insights into how health crises affect FDI, remittances, and broader macroeconomic outcomes, they tend to adopt a country-specific lens, often overlooking the broader regional dynamics that such shocks can trigger. In particular, there remains limited empirical evidence on whether neighboring countries, which may not experience widespread infection but are geographically and economically interconnected with affected nations, also face disruptions in foreign investment or shifts in remittance patterns.

This oversight is critical. Epidemics like Ebola do not respect national borders when it comes to economic perception and behavioral responses. Even countries without confirmed cases may suffer reputational spillovers, border closures, trade disruptions, or reductions in capital flows simply due to proximity and perceived contagion risk. Migration ties can also extend the economic consequences of an epidemic to neighboring states, as diasporas respond to crises in nearby home countries.

The impact of epidemics on financial infows towards hurt countries and their neighbors remain uncovered. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the impact of the Ebola epidemic on FDI and remittance flows towards 28 African countries, including both Ebola-affected nations and their immediate neighbors. By extending the analysis beyond the directly affected countries, we explore whether proximity to the outbreak influenced economic behavior in surrounding areas. Our central hypothesis is that while Ebola negatively affects FDI by increasing perceived risk and disrupting economic activity, it may also lead to an increase in remittances, as migrants step in to support households during times of health and financial distress, in particular in nearby countries connected through borders, migration networks, or economic ties.

To examine the impact of the Ebola epidemic on FDI and remittance flows, this study employs the Local Projection Method (LPM) as its main empirical approach. This flexible framework allows us to estimate the dynamic effects of epidemic shocks over time, without imposing restrictive assumptions on the underlying data structure. Through this method, we capture both the immediate and delayed responses of financial flows to health crises.

Yet, the relationship between epidemics and external financial flows may not be strictly one-directional. Concerns about endogeneity arise, particularly due to the possibility of reverse causality. Countries with higher levels of FDI, for example, may have stronger institutions, more robust healthcare systems, or greater crisis-management capacity, factors that could influence the severity or spread of an epidemic. The latter happens to be idiosyncratic. Similarly, remittances may enhance household resilience and health-seeking

behavior, potentially shaping outbreak outcomes themselves. To address these concerns and reinforce the credibility of our findings, we complement the LPM results with estimates from the System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). This dynamic panel technique helps mitigate bias from endogenous regressors and accounts for unobserved heterogeneity across countries.

To carry out this analysis, we construct a novel panel dataset covering the period 2000 to 2019, drawing from the World Development Indicators (WDI), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and the World Health Organization (WHO).

Our empirical strategy proceeds in three stages: (i) we first assess the short-term effects of the 2014–2016 Ebola outbreak across all 28 countries in our sample; (ii) we then examine longer-term effects in the 11 most affected countries over the full 2000–2019 period, encompassing multiple outbreak episodes; and (iii) we analyze the response of neighboring countries during the 2014–2016 crisis, exploring how geographic proximity may shape exposure to economic disruptions. By combining two empirical methods across different samples and time horizons, this study offers a clear view of how epidemic shocks influence external financial flows—both in the immediate aftermath and over the longer term.

In doing so, Our work bridges the gap between two strands of the literature. The first pertains to the determinants of financial inflows (FDI and remittances). The second strand of the literature relates to the impact of epidemics that were examined on different domestic outcomes such as growth, employment, but seldom on foreign capital inflows.

Our results confirm our expectations: Ebola shocks are associated with a significant decline in FDI inflows and a concurrent rise in remittance receipts. This divergence reflects the dual nature of financial flows during epidemics—where investor confidence deteriorates, but migrant networks respond with increased financial support, highlighting their contrasting roles in economic resilience.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the data and methodology. Section 3 discusses the empirical results. Section 4 highlights the main findings, and the final section concludes with policy implications for managing external financial flows in the context of epidemic shocks.

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

This study employs annual data from 2000 to 2019 for a panel of 28 countries. The analysis focuses on two key dependent variables: foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows and remittance inflows, both expressed as a percentage of GDP. To control for country-specific characteristics that may influence these flows, we include several covariates, grouped into

five categories: macroeconomic indicators, market conditions, demographic factors, institutional quality, and structural characteristics. Each control variable is selected based on its relevance in the literature and its theoretical link to FDI or remittance behavior.

- **Macroeconomic Indicators:** GDP per capita (constant 2010 US dollars) reflects the level of economic development. Higher GDP per capita is typically associated with greater market size and stronger institutional capacity, attracting more FDI (Poelhekke and Van Der Ploeg [2013]; Azzimonti [2019]). In contrast, remittances often respond counter-cyclically, decreasing as economic conditions improve in the home country (Chan and Zheng [2017]). In addition, GDP growth (annual %) is included to capture short-term economic performance. Rapid growth may attract FDI by signaling dynamic market potential and profitability (Julio and Yook [2016]), whereas for remittances, higher growth may reduce the financial need for support from abroad.
- **Market Conditions:** Inflation, measured as the annual percentage change in the consumer price index, captures macroeconomic stability. High inflation tends to deter FDI due to higher uncertainty and reduced investment returns (Julio and Yook [2016]), and may also reduce remittance inflows by eroding the real value of transfers.
- **Demographic Factors:** The age dependency ratio is included to account for demographic pressure. A higher ratio typically leads to greater remittance inflows, as migrants send money to support dependent family members (Chan and Zheng [2017]). Its impact on FDI is expected to be limited or indirect. Additionally, the share of services in GDP is included only in the remittance model, since a higher share of services often reflects an urban and service-oriented economy where migrants are more likely to originate and remit funds.
- **Institutional Quality:** Political stability is an important factor for both FDI and remittances. Countries with stable political environments are more likely to attract long-term foreign investment (Azzimonti [2019]) and give migrants greater confidence in the safety of their transfers. We also include the Gini coefficient to measure income inequality. Higher inequality may discourage FDI by increasing social and political risks and may increase remittances if migrants aim to reduce inequality within their families (Chan and Zheng [2017]).
- **Structural Characteristics:** Total tax rate (as a percentage of commercial profits) is included in the FDI model, as higher taxes can deter foreign investors by lowering net returns (Julio and Yook [2016]). Trade openness, measured as the sum of exports and imports as a percentage of GDP, is also included for FDI, since open economies often present more attractive opportunities for investment (Poelhekke and Van Der Ploeg [2013]).

The panel dataset includes 28 African countries, comprising both Ebola-affected and unaffected countries, allowing for cross-country variation in exposure to the epidemic. Data are sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and the World Health Organization (WHO).

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the dataset, we present three key tables.

Table 1: **Descriptive statistics of all variables of interest**

Variables	Definition	Source	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max	Obs
Remit(%gdp)	Personal remittances, received(% GDP)	WDI	3.068	3.581	0	14.063	555
FDI(%gdp)	Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)	WDI	4.24	5.55	- 3.04	28.216	588
logGDP(per capita)	GDP per capita (%current US)	WDI	6.713	0.845	5.034	8.886	616
Inflation	Inflation, consumer prices (annual)	WDI	6.848	6.460	- 0.606	23.563	578
GDP(growth)	GDP growth (annual %)	WDI	4.440	3.386	- 2.680	10. 548	615
Population	Population density (people per sq. km of land area)	WDI	85.721	101.188	2.614	532.888	588
logDependency	Age dependency ratio (of working-age population)	WDI	4.474	0.123	3.878	4.717	616
logServices	Services, value added (constant 2015 US\$)	WDI	22.286	1.490	19.227	26.361	591
Gini	Gini	WDI	- 0.481	0.680	-1	0.571	559
Political	Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism	WDI	- 0.752	0.827	- 2.665	1.219	560
Totaltax	Total tax and contribution rate	WDI	61.082	59.473	15	288.2	411
Trade	Trade (%GDP)	WDI	60.947	26.396	21.641	133.108	589
Lifeex	Life expectancy at birth, total (years)	WDI	57.725	5.967	39.441	73.166	588
Ebola	number of Ebola-related deaths or a dummy	CDC - WHO	20.560	186.902	0	2617	616

Note: This table provides definitions, sources and summary statistics for the variables used in the analysis. The sample extends from 2000 to 2022 of the variables

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the variables used in the analysis. It includes measures of central tendency (mean), variability (standard deviation), and the range (minimum and maximum values) for each variable. This table helps in understanding the basic distribution and variability of the data.

On average, countries in the sample received remittances equivalent to 3.07% of their GDP, while foreign direct investment inflows averaged 4.24% of GDP. The mean GDP per capita (in logarithmic form) is approximately 6.71, which corresponds to a moderate income level across the countries studied. Several variables, including GDP per capita, services value added, and age dependency ratio, are log-transformed to reduce skewness and improve interpretability. Inflation rates vary widely, with a mean of 6.85%, suggesting diverse macroeconomic environments. The average GDP growth rate is 4.44%, indicating relatively strong economic performance over the period.

Demographic and structural indicators, such as the age dependency ratio (log value of 4.47) and services sector value added (mean log value of 22.29), highlight the development patterns of the sample countries. Political stability has a negative average score of -0.75, indicating overall political risk. The Gini coefficient has been normalized or centered for the analysis, which may result in negative values. Tax burdens are highly variable, with

an average total tax rate of 61.08%. Trade openness averages around 61% of GDP, and life expectancy stands at 57.73 years on average, reflecting relatively low levels of health outcomes in the region.

Regarding the epidemic variable, the mean value of the Ebola indicator is 20.56, with a maximum of 2.617, indicating the presence of severe health shocks in some countries during the study period. For the regression analysis, a dummy variable was created to capture whether a country experienced an Ebola outbreak in a given year.

Table 4 and 5 presented in Appendix 5, provide a comprehensive view of how FDI and remittances are related to various economic, demographic, and policy factors. The first matrix illustrates the pairwise correlations between FDI and variables such as economic conditions, demographic factors, and policy measures, helping to identify potential determinants of FDI flows. The second matrix focuses on Remittance, showing how it correlates with similar variables, thereby elucidating the linear relationships that might influence remittance inflows.

2.1.1 Ebola Shock Variable Construction

To identify the timing and exposure of countries to the Ebola epidemic, we construct three distinct Ebola shock variables to capture different dimensions of the outbreak's impact: direct exposure, regional spillovers, and general epidemic periods.

- **Ebola:** A binary variable equal to 1 for all countries in the sample during the core epidemic years (2014–2016), and 0 otherwise. This captures the general regional shock associated with heightened uncertainty and contagion fears, even in countries without confirmed cases.
- **Ebola_Affected:** A country-year dummy equal to 1 only for countries that experienced at least one confirmed Ebola outbreak between 2000 and 2019 and only in the specific years when cases were reported. This variable isolates the effect of direct health shocks.
- **Ebola_Neighbors:** A binary variable equal to 1 for countries geographically neighboring the directly affected ones, but only during 2014–2016. This variable accounts for regional spillover effects, such as reduced investor confidence or border closures that may influence economic outcomes despite the absence of domestic cases.

Using these three alternative definitions allows us to explore how the impact of Ebola varies depending on whether a country was directly hit, exposed through proximity, or affected by broader regional dynamics. This distinction is particularly important in the context of foreign direct investment and remittances, which may respond differently to localized health risks versus widespread epidemic uncertainty.

To provide an initial overview of the behavior of financial flows during health crises, this section examines trends in foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittances over the period 2000–2019, with particular focus on the years of the Ebola outbreak (2014–2016). We analyze both the distribution and the dynamic evolution of these two variables across Ebola-affected and neighboring countries.

Figure 1: Changes in FDI and Remittances during the period 2000–2019

Note: Authors' calculations based on data from the WDI, CDC, and WHO.

Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and remittance as a percentage of GDP for both Ebola-affected and neighboring countries. The FDI exhibit a sharp decline during the Ebola crisis. Starting in 2012 for affected countries and 2014 for neighboring countries, FDI inflows fell significantly and reached their lowest point in 2014 and 2016, likely due to heightened investor uncertainty and disruptions caused by the epidemic. Although there was some recovery in subsequent years, the overall trend suggests that the Ebola crisis had a more lasting negative impact on FDI inflows, as investor confidence was slow to return.

In contrast, in Ebola-affected countries, remittance inflows rose sharply between 2012 and 2015, peaking in 2015 during the height of the epidemic. This surge likely reflects an increase in financial support from diaspora communities responding to heightened health and economic needs during the crisis. In contrast, neighboring countries exhibited a relatively stable remittance trend over the same period, with only modest increases. However, in 2016, remittance inflows dropped significantly in affected countries and declined slightly

in neighboring countries as well. This post-peak downturn may suggest a normalization of flows after the crisis period, or temporary disruptions in the channels used to send remittances. Overall, the figure underscores the critical, though time-sensitive, role that remittances can play in reducing the economic effects of health shocks, particularly for the most directly impacted populations.

2.2 Methodology

This study investigates the impact of the Ebola epidemic on foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittance inflows across 28 African countries over the period 2000–2019. Given the need to capture both the dynamic short-run effects of epidemic shocks and address potential endogeneity in the data, we adopt a two-step estimation strategy.

First, we estimate impulse response functions using the local projection method (LPM), as introduced by Jordà [2005]. The LPM framework is particularly suitable for our context because it allows us to trace the dynamic response of financial flows in the years following an Ebola outbreak, without requiring full specification of the underlying data-generating process. This temporal analysis is particularly important in the case of the Ebola epidemic. Epidemic shocks are indeed often unanticipated and generate sudden, widespread uncertainty. While investors may in reality respond with caution based on early warning signs, our focus is on the dynamic adjustment following the outbreak. The local projection method (LPM) allows us to trace how FDI inflows evolve in the aftermath, highlighting both immediate disruptions and more persistent effects driven by lingering risk perceptions. This helps us understand the duration and asymmetry of the shock’s impact on investor confidence and capital mobility. The LPM also accommodates nonlinear and heterogeneous responses over time, making it particularly well-suited to studying the cross-country dynamics of epidemic shocks. This forms the basis of our baseline estimation strategy.

Second, as a robustness check, we employ the System Generalized Method of Moments (System GMM) to estimate the long-run structural relationships between Ebola shocks and financial inflows, while addressing potential endogeneity concerns. In the context of our analysis, endogeneity may arise from several sources. First, there is a risk of reverse causality: countries with lower FDI or remittance inflows may have weaker health surveillance and reporting systems, which could affect the measurement and international response to epidemic outbreaks. Second, unobserved country-specific factors—such as institutional quality, governance, or diaspora engagement—may simultaneously influence both exposure to epidemics and financial flows. Finally, both FDI and remittances are persistent over time, meaning that past values influence current outcomes, further complicating causal interpretation. System GMM is particularly well suited to address these challenges in dynamic panel data settings. It allows us to control for country-specific fixed effects, account for the

persistence of financial flows, and use internal instruments (lagged variables) to correct for potential biases arising from omitted variables or simultaneity. This is especially relevant in the context of highly localized and irregular shocks such as epidemics, where traditional fixed-effects estimators may fall short.

Together, these two complementary approaches allow us to uncover both the short-run dynamics and longer-run relationships between epidemic shocks and external financial flows in African countries.

2.3 Baseline Empirical Specification

The general empirical model used throughout the paper is specified as follows:

$$y_{it} = \alpha + \gamma \text{EbolaShock}_{it} + \mathbf{X}'_{it}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- y_{it} is the dependent variable: either foreign direct investment or remittances (both as % of GDP);
- EbolaShock_{it} captures the intensity of the epidemic (e.g., number of Ebola-related deaths or a dummy);
- \mathbf{X}_{it} is a vector of control variables;
- μ_i and λ_t are country and year fixed effects;
- ε_{it} is the error term.

The control variables in \mathbf{X}_{it} include GDP per capita (log), inflation, GDP growth, population, trade openness, tax rate, life expectancy, Gini coefficient, political stability index, dependency ratio, and value added in the services sector.

GDP per capita, often used as a proxy for market potential and economic stability, is expected to have a positive influence on FDI inflows (Asiedu [2002], Chakrabarti [2001]), while its association with remittances may be negative, as higher income levels tend to reduce the reliance on transfers from abroad (Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz [2009]). Inflation enters the model to capture macroeconomic uncertainty; higher inflation is generally seen as a deterrent for investors due to rising costs and increased volatility as rising price harm savings (Bengoa and Sanchez-Robles [2003]), although its effect on remittances remains less conclusive (Faini [2006]). In a similar vein, GDP growth is commonly viewed as a signal of economic dynamism and potential profitability, thus likely attracting greater FDI (Moosa [2002]).

The role of demographic and geographic characteristics is also considered. While higher

population density can signal a larger domestic market and labor availability (Wheeler and Mody [1992]), it may also reflect pressures on infrastructure and resources. Trade openness, reflecting a country’s level of integration into global markets, is generally found to support both FDI and remittance inflows by enhancing economic connectivity and reducing transaction barriers (Borensztein et al. [1998], Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz [2009]). Conversely, higher tax rates may reduce the net returns for investors, thereby discouraging foreign capital (Hines [1993]).

Life expectancy, as a proxy for human capital and health system strength, can positively influence both FDI and remittances by signaling higher productivity and quality of life (Alsan et al. [2006], Beine et al. [2011]). Income inequality, measured by the Gini index, may play a dual role: excessive inequality can create social and political instability, undermining investor confidence, yet it may also reflect untapped markets and potential opportunities (Teo and Wong [2021]). In line with this, political stability is a critical determinant, with more stable environments generally attracting both foreign investors and migrant remittances (Globerman and Shapiro [2003], Daude and Stein [2007]).

Finally, demographic burdens are captured through the age dependency ratio, which is often positively associated with remittance flows, as migrants send funds to support children and elderly family members left behind (Adams and Cuecuecha [2010]). A larger services sector, meanwhile, can signal greater economic diversification and development, making a country more attractive for long-term investment (Alfaro et al. [2004]).

2.4 Local Projection Method (LPM)

To trace the dynamic effects of Ebola shocks over time, we estimate impulse response functions using the local projection method of Jordà [2005]. This method allows for flexible estimation of responses at different horizons without imposing restrictive assumptions on the underlying process. The local projection equation is:

$$y_{i,t+h} = \alpha_h + \gamma_h \text{EbolaShock}_{it} + \mathbf{X}'_{it} \boldsymbol{\beta}_h + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t+h} \quad (2)$$

We estimate this specification for several horizons $h = 0, 1, 2, 3$ to assess both pre-trends and the short- to medium-term impact of the shock. We conduct three sets of local projection estimations:

1. For all 28 countries during the 2014-2016 Ebola crisis;
2. For the 11 most affected countries over the full period (2000-2019);
3. For neighboring countries during 2014-2016, to analyze regional spillovers.

2.5 System GMM Estimation

A key challenge in estimating the effects of epidemic shocks on foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittances is the issue of endogeneity. First, the relationship between epidemics and FDI may be bidirectional: epidemics can reduce investor confidence and increase the perceived risk of doing business, while low levels of FDI may reflect deeper structural weaknesses, such as poor healthcare systems or weak institutions, that make a country more vulnerable to outbreaks. This two-way relationship creates the risk of reverse causality. Second, several control variables commonly used in the analysis of capital flows may also be endogenous. Variables such as GDP growth, trade openness, inflation, and epidemic-related deaths may be jointly determined with FDI or remittances, or may suffer from measurement error. If these issues are not addressed, they can lead to biased and inconsistent estimates.

To deal with these concerns, we use the System Generalized Method of Moments (System GMM) estimator developed by Blundell and Bond [2023]. This approach is well suited for dynamic panel data models with a short time dimension and helps control for endogeneity, unobserved heterogeneity, and reverse causality. In both the FDI and remittances models, we include a lagged dependent variable to account for persistence over time. We also treat potentially endogenous control variables, such as GDP growth, trade, inflation, and epidemic-related deaths—using their lagged values to help isolate their causal effects. System GMM combines equations in first differences and in levels, and uses internal instruments based on past values of the variables. The general form of the dynamic model is:

$$y_{it} = \alpha + \rho, y_{it} - 1 + \gamma, \text{EbolaShock} * it + \mathbf{X} * it' \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

To eliminate unobserved country-specific effects (μ_i), we first-difference the equation:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \rho, \Delta y_{it} - 1 + \gamma, \Delta \text{EbolaShock} * it + \Delta \mathbf{X} * it' \boldsymbol{\beta} + \Delta \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

However, many macroeconomic variables are highly persistent, and using lagged levels as instruments in the differenced equation alone may result in weak instruments. System GMM addresses this issue by also using lagged differences as instruments in the levels equation, which improves the efficiency and consistency of the estimates.

We implement the two-step System GMM estimator and apply the following diagnostic checks to assess the validity of our estimation:

- **Hansen J test for instrument validity:** This test evaluates the overall validity of the instruments used in the model. Specifically, it tests the null hypothesis that the instruments are exogenous—that is, uncorrelated with the error term. A high p -value suggests that the instruments are valid, while a very low p -value may indicate overidentification or instrument proliferation, which can bias the results. Since GMM

estimation often involves a large number of instruments, this test is critical to ensure credible inference.

- **Arellano–Bond test for autocorrelation:** This test helps check whether the model suffers from serial correlation in the error terms. After differencing the equation, some autocorrelation is expected at the first order. However, second-order autocorrelation would indicate a problem with the model and that the instruments used might not be valid. If the test does not find significant second-order autocorrelation, we can be more confident that the model is well specified and the instruments are appropriate.

3 Results

This section presents the main findings from the Local Projection Method (LPM), our primary empirical approach, which allows us to trace the dynamic effects of epidemic shocks on foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittances over time. We then assess the robustness of our results using two complementary estimation strategies: a standard fixed-effects panel model and a dynamic System GMM estimator to address potential endogeneity.

3.1 Dynamic Effects of Ebola on FDI and Remittances: Local Projection Results

To examine how the impact of Ebola on foreign direct investment (FDI) evolves over time and varies by exposure, we estimate impulse response functions (IRFs) using the local projection method for three distinct samples: (i) all 28 African countries during the core outbreak years (2014–2016), (ii) Ebola-affected countries over the full 2000–2019 period, and (iii) neighboring countries during the same outbreak window. The results are illustrated in Figures 2c, 2a, and 2b, respectively.

Figure 2: Impulse Response of FDI to Ebola Outbreak Shock

(a) Affected Countries

(b) Neighboring Countries

(c) All countries

Note: Each panel shows the impulse response of FDI inflows to an Ebola outbreak shock using the local projection method. The solid line represents the point estimate, and the vertical bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. Panel (a) shows results for directly affected countries, (b) for neighboring countries, and (c) for all countries in the sample.

The analysis reveals Ebola's negative impact on FDI across all country groups, though the effects differ in timing and intensity. In the full sample of 28 African countries (Figure 2c), FDI shows a steady decline, reaching about -3.5 percentage points by year five. This pattern aligns with studies showing that health crises trigger regional investor caution, as risks spread beyond directly affected areas [Ghosh and Renna, 2015].

The eleven most affected countries (Figure 2a) experience a sharp initial drop of nearly 6 percentage points, echoing findings that epidemics cause immediate capital flight from high-risk zones [Karlsson et al., 2013]. The slow recovery over five years supports research on lasting investor skepticism after repeated outbreaks [Yu et al., 2021].

Neighboring countries (Figure 2b) show a different pattern: a rapid two-year decline followed by recovery. This matches studies suggesting geographic proximity alone causes temporary investment hesitancy [Bloom et al., 1998], unless paired with direct exposure [Bloom et al., 2014].

Our findings reveal that while the Ebola outbreak led to a sharp but short-lived drop in FDI for directly affected countries, regional neighbors experienced a slower but more prolonged decline. In contrast, a broad-based investor retreat persisted across the region, suggesting that fear and uncertainty were not confined to the epicenter but spilled over both spatially and temporally. Three key insights emerge. First, epidemic severity appears to shape FDI recovery timelines, as evidenced by the stark contrast between directly affected and neighboring nations. Second, regional risk perceptions matter—even countries without active outbreaks may suffer investment slowdowns due to heightened uncertainty [Azemar and Desbordes, 2009]. Third, the persistent FDI decline in affected countries underscores how health crises can erode institutional credibility and investor trust [Hassan et al., 2023]. These findings highlight the need for coordinated cross-border health-investment strategies. As Bloom et al. [2019] emphasize, mitigating epidemic-driven capital flight requires not only swift health interventions but also long-term measures to reassure and attract investors.

Figure 3c, 3a, and 3b present the dynamic responses of remittance inflows (as a share of GDP) to Ebola outbreak shocks, estimated using the local projection method across three different samples: (i) all 28 African countries, (ii) Ebola-affected countries, and (iii) neighboring countries. These estimates allow us to assess not only the immediate effect of the crisis but also the persistence and evolution of remittance responses over time.

Figure 3: Impulse Response of Remittances to Ebola Outbreak Shock

(a) Affected Countries

(b) Neighboring Countries

(c) All countries

Note: Each panel shows the impulse response of Remittances inflow to an Ebola outbreak shock using the local projection method. The solid line represents the point estimate, and the vertical bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. Panel (a) shows results for directly affected countries, (b) for neighboring countries, and (c) for all countries in the sample.

The analysis shows different patterns in remittance flows across country groups. In the full sample (Figure 3c), remittances gradually increase by about 0.4 percentage points of GDP. This steady rise aligns with studies showing that migrants maintain stable support during systemic shocks [Lueth and Ruiz-Arranz, 2008]. It may reflect regional solidarity and learning from past health crises, consistent with findings that diasporas adapt their transfer strategies over time [Mohapatra et al., 2012].

In countries directly affected by Ebola (Figure 3a), remittances initially surge in response to the crisis, similar to patterns seen in natural disasters [Shastri and Garg, 2022]. After a brief decline, remittances strongly increase again, exceeding 1 percentage point of GDP. This dual response supports the idea that remittances act as a form of insurance

during crises [Ratha, 2007], helping households cope with immediate shocks and supporting longer-term recovery [Yang, 2008]. The delayed resurgence echoes findings that remittances aid in rebuilding livelihoods when public services are disrupted [Beuermann and McKelvey, 2016].

Neighboring countries show a modest response (Figure 3b), supporting the notion that remittances are targeted at specific households rather than broader regional risks [Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz, 2009]. While some studies suggest that general risk awareness influences remittance behavior [Ponce et al., 2011], our results indicate that migrants prioritize direct family needs over geographic proximity alone [Amuedo-Dorantes and Pozo, 2007].

These findings collectively enhance our understanding of remittances as stabilizers during health crises. The pattern in directly affected countries confirms that remittances serve as both investments and insurance payments [Chami et al., 2005], while the persistence across the full sample supports the idea that institutional factors play a role [Álvarez Tinajero, 2015]. This synthesis shows how crisis characteristics shape the magnitude and timing of migrant-led risk mitigation.

3.2 Robustness Check:

3.2.1 Estimation of fixed effects

To assess the consistency of our main results, we begin with a standard fixed-effects model as a baseline. This approach captures average relationships between Ebola shocks, remittances, and FDI across countries and time, controlling for unobserved heterogeneity through country and year fixed effects. While this static model does not account for dynamic adjustments or delayed responses, it provides a useful point of comparison.

Table 2: Country and Time Fixed Effects Estimation: The Impact of Ebola on Remittances and FDI

Variables	Remittances (FE)	FDI (FE)
Ln.GDPpc	-2.743**	-2.378*
Inflation	-0.027*	-0.097
GDP growth	0.034	0.061
Ln.Services	3.145	-
Political Stability	0.055	-0.008
Gini	0.099	-0.458
Population	0.006	-0.006
Ln.Dependency	3.257**	-
Total Tax Rate	-	-0.000
Trade Openness	-	0.079*
Life Expectancy	-	0.334
Ebola	0.001**	-0.002***
Observations	482	398
R^2	0.114	0.250

Note: This table reports fixed effects estimations with country and year fixed effects. The variable *Ebola* is a dummy equal to 1 during outbreak years. Standard errors are clustered at the country level. *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01. Author's calculations based on WDI, CDC, and WHO.

Table 2 reports fixed-effects estimation results examining the relationship between Ebola outbreaks, remittances, and FDI as percentages of GDP. By including country and year fixed effects, the model accounts for time-invariant heterogeneity and macroeconomic shocks common to all countries.

The findings indicate that Ebola shocks have a statistically significant and positive association with remittances, suggesting that remittance inflows increased during Ebola outbreaks. This is consistent with the literature highlighting the counter-cyclical nature of remittances, as diaspora communities increase transfers to support affected households in times of crisis.

In contrast, the effect of Ebola on FDI is negative and highly significant, reflecting the vulnerability of investment flows to health-related uncertainty. Epidemic shocks likely erode investor confidence, disrupt supply chains, and raise perceived country risk, all of which discourage foreign capital inflows.

Control variables behave largely as expected. GDP per capita is negatively associated with both remittances and FDI, possibly reflecting saturation effects or changing relative needs. Trade openness shows a positive and significant effect on FDI, highlighting the role

of global integration in attracting investment.

While the fixed-effects estimates offer valuable insights into the average relationship between Ebola outbreaks, remittances, and FDI, they do not account for how these effects evolve over time. To explore the temporal dynamics of these relationships, the analysis now turns to the local projection method, which enables the estimation of impulse response functions and the identification of short- and medium-term patterns in the behavior of external financial flows surrounding epidemic shocks.

3.2.2 Addressing Endogeneity with System GMM

While the local projection estimates offer valuable insights into the dynamic responses of FDI and remittances to Ebola shocks, concerns around endogeneity remain critical for causal interpretation. In particular, variables such as GDP per capita, political stability, and population may be jointly determined with external financial flows, raising issues of simultaneity and reverse causality. For instance, while higher political stability may attract FDI, FDI inflows themselves may contribute to improved institutional quality and economic governance. Similarly, remittance flows may influence and be influenced by economic development or demographic structure.

To address these concerns, we implement the System Generalized Method of Moments (System GMM), which provides a consistent and efficient estimation strategy for dynamic panel models with potential endogeneity. By using internal instruments based on lagged levels and first differences of the regressors, System GMM controls for unobserved heterogeneity, measurement error, and feedback effects between the dependent and independent variables. This method is particularly well-suited to our context, where many explanatory variables exhibit persistence over time and traditional fixed effects or OLS estimators may be biased or inconsistent.

The GMM estimates serve as a robustness check for the local projection results, allowing us to assess the stability of our main findings under an alternative identification strategy that addresses endogeneity explicitly.

Table 3: System GMM Estimations of the Relationship between Ebola, Remittances, and FDI

Variable	Remittances	FDI
L.Remit(%GDP)	0.896***	–
L.FDI(%GDP)	–	0.456*
Ln.GDPpc	0.269	–1.294*
Inflation	0.145***	-0.007
GDP growth	0.126**	-0.064
Ln.Services	–0.307**	–
Politic	0.201	0.727
Gini	0.368***	-0.324
Population	0.000	-0.007
Ln.Dependency	-0.120	–
Total tax	–	-0.002
Trade	–	0.023
Life expectancy	–	0.065
Ebola	0.001**	–0.003**
Obs	453	398
Number of groups	28	28
AR(1)	0.013	0.005
AR(2)	0.749	0.773
Hansen test	0.410	0.586
Number of Instruments	20	21

Note: This table reports System GMM estimations. The variable *Ebola* is a dummy equal to 1 during outbreak years. Standard errors are clustered at the country level. *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01. Author’s calculations based on WDI, CDC, and WHO.

The results obtained from our estimation using the System GMM method, as presented in Table 9 (Columns 1 and 2), align with our expectations and support the findings from Table 4. In the first column, we find that the Ebola variable has a positive and significant effect on remittances. This outcome reinforces the notion that individuals tend to behave altruistically in critical situations, such as epidemic outbreaks in their countries of origin. They increase their remittance contributions to support their families and help mitigate the damages caused by the crisis. It could also be a sign of a strategic motive from the migrant or of insurance or investment behavior from the family ([Rapoport and Docquier, 2006]). These findings are consistent with previous studies ([Stark and Bloom, 1985, Lucas and Stark, 1985, Johnson and Whitelaw, 1974, Chami et al., 2005, Benmamoun and Lehnert, 2013, Singh et al., 2011]) that have explored the relationship between health crises and remittance patterns.

Turning to the effect of the Ebola outbreak on foreign direct investment (FDI), the results in the second column of Table 9 are consistent with our expectations. We find that a 1 percent increase in Ebola prevalence is associated with a 0.45 percent decline in FDI inflows. This negative relationship suggests that epidemic shocks influence investor confidence and decision-making, likely through increased uncertainty, heightened risk perception, and potential disruptions to economic activity. These findings are consistent with previous research documenting the adverse effects of health crises on investment behavior (Ajide et al. [2022]; Chiappini et al. [2022]; Immurana [2021]; Alsan et al. [2006]).

Firstly, the outbreak creates a high level of uncertainty among investors, which directly contributes to the decline in FDI inflows. The severe health crisis raises concerns about the stability of the affected countries' economies and the safety of investments. Investors become more cautious and hesitant to allocate capital to regions grappling with a severe epidemic, resulting in reduced FDI. Secondly, the Ebola outbreak severely disrupted economic activities in affected countries, particularly in key sectors such as agriculture, mining, and services. While these economies are not deeply integrated into global supply chains, the crisis led to labor shortages, mobility restrictions, and business closures, which significantly hindered production and trade. For example, mining operations were scaled back due to health risks and a reduced workforce, and quarantine measures and market closures disrupted agricultural activities. These conditions created an uncertain and challenging environment for doing business, discouraging foreign investors from entering or expanding in the region [Corps, 2015, Bank, 2014].

The impacts of other explanatory variables are equally notable. The first model suggests that GDP growth, inflation, and the Gini coefficient have a positive and significant impact on remittances, while services and value-added have a negative and significant relationship with remittances. Additionally, remittances play a shock-absorbing role when adverse economic shocks decrease incomes in their home country. In the second model, a negative and significant relationship exists between GDP per capita and FDI, indicating a growing economy, stable investment climate, and improved infrastructure. Although there exists both a negative and positive relationship between total tax, trade, and foreign investment, which is entirely consistent with theoretical perspectives and analysis, we were unable to obtain significant results.

3.3 Additional Robustness Checks: Controlling for Confounding Events and Outliers

Beyond econometric concerns, we also account for other potential confounding factors that could distort the observed relationship between the Ebola outbreak and external financial

flows. Specifically, we conduct a set of robustness tests by introducing additional controls and sample exclusions:

- **Conflict and Malaria:** We include variables capturing the incidence of armed conflict and malaria prevalence, both of which are known to influence FDI and remittance flows. Armed conflict deters investment but may boost remittances as diaspora networks respond to crises. Malaria, as an endemic health burden, affects labor productivity and government spending. Including these variables ensures that the effects attributed to Ebola are not conflated with broader health or security shocks.
- **Exclusion of the 2008 Global Financial Crisis:** To rule out contamination from global financial trends, we exclude the period corresponding to the 2008 financial crisis, which saw a sharp contraction in global FDI and remittance flows.
- **Exclusion of Nigeria:** Given its outsized role in the region’s FDI and remittance flows, we exclude Nigeria from the sample to test whether the main findings are driven by this influential outlier.

Across all specifications, the Ebola shock variable remains statistically significant and shows consistent effects. We find that Ebola outbreaks are linked to a drop in FDI inflows and a rise in remittance receipts. This supports the idea that while epidemics tend to scare off investors, they also lead to increased financial support from migrants. These results add confidence to our findings and suggest that the impact of Ebola on external financial flows is not simply the result of other shocks or the influence of large economies in the sample (see Appendix 5 for full results).

4 Conclusion and Policy Implications

This study examines the impact of the Ebola epidemic on foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittances across 28 African countries over the period 2000–2019. By combining fixed effects estimations, local projection methods (LPM), and system GMM models, we provide an in-depth analysis of how epidemic shocks influence external financial flows—both in countries directly affected by the outbreak and in their neighboring economies.

Our findings show that Ebola outbreaks have a substantial and persistent negative effect on FDI inflows. This pattern is most pronounced in countries that experienced repeated or severe outbreaks, where investor confidence was likely undermined by heightened health risks, disruptions to business activity, and deteriorating macroeconomic conditions. Even neighboring countries not directly affected by the virus experienced significant spillover effects, with FDI declining—albeit more gradually and temporarily—suggesting that epidemic risk perceptions extend beyond borders.

In contrast, remittance inflows tend to increase following Ebola outbreaks, especially in the most affected countries. This response reflects the countercyclical nature of remittances and the important role of diaspora networks in providing financial support during health emergencies. While neighboring countries exhibit weaker remittance responses, the overall evidence confirms that remittances act as a stabilizing force in times of crisis, offsetting part of the income and welfare losses incurred domestically.

These dynamics remain robust across multiple empirical strategies, including controls for endogeneity through system GMM, and sensitivity tests accounting for armed conflict, malaria prevalence, the 2008 global recession, and outlier effects from dominant economies like Nigeria. Together, the results emphasize the asymmetric nature of external financial flows during health shocks: FDI contracts in the face of uncertainty, while remittances expand as a form of social insurance.

From a policy perspective, while international organizations often emphasize the economic costs of health shocks within affected countries, more attention should be paid to the way these shocks influence the behavior of economic agents in surrounding regions. For policymakers, this represents a missed opportunity to develop regional preparedness plans, cross-border cooperation mechanisms, and financial buffers that account not only for direct health impacts but also for broader contagion through markets, migration, and perceptions.

Our outcomes underscore the need to strengthen public health systems in order to reduce the economic cost of disease outbreaks by preserving investor confidence and maintaining productive capacity. At the same time, governments and development partners should recognize the critical role of remittances in crisis response. Policies that reduce transaction costs, improve access to financial services, and foster diaspora engagement can enhance the resilience of remittance flows during emergencies.

Finally, the regional nature of the effects documented in this study calls for coordinated cross-border responses. Health crises do not respect national boundaries, and neither do their economic consequences. Regional integration, surveillance, and joint policy action can help mitigate both the health and economic spillovers of future epidemics, preserving financial stability and development prospects across the continent.

5 Appendix

Table 4: **Correlation matrix**

	FDI(%gdp)	logGDPpc	Inflation	Totaltax	Trade	GDPg	Population	Lifeex	Gini	Politic	Ebola
FDI(%gdp)	1.00										
logGDPpc	0.04	1.00									
Inflation	0.02	-0.13	1.00								
Totaltax	-0.02	-0.27	0.07	1.00							
Trade	0.48	0.36	-0.09	-0.07	1.00						
GDPg	0.01	-0.10	0.00	-0.06	0.02	1.00					
Population	-0.17	-0.22	0.00	0.09	-0.31	0.04	1.00				
Lifeex	0.09	0.48	-0.18	-0.22	0.17	-0.12	0.14	1.00			
Gini	0.03	0.11	-0.17	-0.18	0.10	-0.14	-0.09	0.32	1.00		
Politic	0.15	0.26	-0.31	-0.10	0.30	0.04	-0.03	0.22	-0.11	1.00	
Ebola	0.03	-0.02	0.00	-0.02	0.06	-0.09	-0.02	0.00	0.02	-0.00	1.00

Note: This table displays the correlation matrix of FDI and control variables. The authors' calculations are based on data from the World Development Indicators (WDI), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and the World Health Organization (WHO)

Table 5: **Correlation matrix**

	Remit(%gdp)	logGDPpc	Inflation	GDPg	Population	logDependency	logServices	Gini	Politic	Ebola
Remit(%gdp)	1.00									
logGDPpc	0.026	1.00								
Inflation	-0.19	-0.14	1.00							
GDPg	-0.08	-0.12	0.02	1.00						
Population	0.15	-0.23	0.00	0.05	1.00					
logDependency	-0.25	-0.55	0.15	0.16	-0.07	1.00				
logServices	-0.32	0.36	0.29	0.11	-0.06	0.09	1.00			
Gini	0.12	0.11	-0.17	-0.15	-0.11	-0.18	-0.02	1.00		
Politic	0.23	0.26	-0.31	0.02	-0.06	-0.29	-0.40	-0.11	1.00	
Ebola	0.08	-0.02	0.00	-0.06	0.01	-0.00	-0.03	0.02	-0.00	1.00

Note: This table displays the correlation matrix of Remittances and control variables. The authors' calculations are based on data from the World Development Indicators (WDI), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and the World Health Organization (WHO).

Table 6: Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations Including War

Variable	System GMM	
	Remittances	FDI
L.Remit(%GDP)	0.895***	-
L.FDI(%GDP)	-	0.452*
Ln.GDPpc	0.219	-1.300*
Inflation	0.147***	-0.011
GDP growth	0.116**	-0.061
Ln.Services	-0.293**	-
Politic	0.135	0.755*
Gini	0.358***	-0.322
Population	0.000	-0.006
Ln.Dependency	-0.430	-
Total tax	-	-0.003
Trade	-	0.024
Life expectancy	-	0.061
Ebola	0.001**	-0.003**
War	-0.757	0.437
Obs	453	398
Number of groups	28	28
AR(1)	0.014	0.005
AR(2)	0.745	0.772
Hansen test	0.411	0.617
Number of Instruments	21	22

Note: This table reports Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations Including War. The variable *Ebola* is a dummy equal to 1 during outbreak years. Standard errors are clustered at the country level. *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01. Author's calculations based on WDI, CDC, and WHO.

Table 7: Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations Including Malaria's Outbreak

Variable	System GMM	
	Remittances	FDI
L.Remit(%GDP)	0.814***	-
L.FDI(%GDP)	-	0.528*
Ln.GDPpc	0.453*	-1.323**
Inflation	0.130***	-0.024
GDP growth	0.125**	-0.090
Ln.Services	-0.394**	-
Politic	0.162	0.781
Gini	0.400***	-0.261
Population	0.246	-0.007
Ln.Dependency	0.358	-
Total tax	-	-0.002
Trade	-	0.008
Life expectancy	-	-0.013
Ebola	0.001**	-0.004**
Malaria	-0.000	-0.004
Obs	453	398
Number of groups	28	28
AR(1)	0.018	0.004
AR(2)	0.804	0.812
Hansen test	0.425	0.725
Number of Instruments	21	23

Note: This table reports Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations Including Malaria's Outbreak. The variable *Ebola* is a dummy equal to 1 during outbreak years. Standard errors are clustered at the country level. *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01. Author's calculations based on WDI, CDC, and WHO.

Table 8: Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations excluding Global Recession of 2008

Variable	System GMM	
	Remittances	FDI
L.Remit(%GDP)	1.049***	-
L.FDI(%GDP)	-	0.429*
Ln.GDPpc	0.130	-1.362*
Inflation	0.170***	-0.015
GDP growth	0.023	0.035
Ln.Services	-0.186	-
Politic	0.297	0.920*
Gini	0.214***	-0.447
Population	0.000	-0.009**
Ln.Dependency	0.604	-
Total tax	-	0.000
Trade	-	0.004
Life expectancy	-	0.0716
Ebola	0.001*	-0.004**
Obs	397	391
Number of groups	28	27
AR(1)	0.003	0.006
AR(2)	0.721	0.776
Hansen test	0.220	0.650
Number of Instruments	24	21

Note: This table reports Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations excluding Global Recession of 2008. The variable *Ebola* is a dummy equal to 1 during outbreak years. Standard errors are clustered at the country level. *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01. Author's calculations based on WDI, CDC, and WHO.

Table 9: Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations excluding Nigeria

Variable	System GMM	
	Remittances	FDI
L.Remit(%GDP)	0.903***	-
L.FDI(%GDP)	-	0.451*
Ln.GDPpc	0.237	-1.476*
Inflation	0.150***	-0.009
GDP growth	0.141**	-0.044
Ln.Services	-0.372**	-
Politic	0.248	0.810*
Gini	0.430***	-0.314
Population	-0.000	-0.008
Ln.Dependency	-0.092	-
Total tax	-	-0.002
Trade	-	0.024
Life expectancy	-	0.088
Ebola	0.001**	-0.003*
Obs	435	391
Number of groups	27	27
AR(1)	0.017	0.006
AR(2)	0.591	0.776
Hansen test	0.404	0.650
Number of Instruments	20	21

Note: The table reports Robustness Test of System GMM Estimations Excluding Nigeria. The variable *Ebola* is a dummy equal to 1 during outbreak years. Standard errors are clustered at the country level. *p < 0.1, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01. Author's calculations based on WDI, CDC, and WHO.

Table 10: **List of the countries that we used in this study**

Countries			
Angola	Cabo Verde	Liberia*	Sudan*
Burundi	Ethiopia	Mali*	Senegal*
Burkina Faso	Gabon*	Mozambique	Sierra Leone*
Cote d'Ivoire	Guinea*	Mauritania	Togo
Cameroon	Gambia, The	Niger	Tanzania
Congo, Dem. Rep.*	Guinea-Bissau	Nigeria*	Uganda*
Congo, Rep.*	Kenya	Rwanda	Zambia

* = Affected Countries

6 Declarations of interest

6.1 Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are publicly available on platforms such as the World Development Indicators (WDI), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and the World Health Organization (WHO).

6.2 Funding details

Not relevant.

6.3 Disclosure of interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

6.4 Consent to publish

All authors declare that they agree with the submission and publication of this manuscript.

6.5 ethics approval statement

Not relevant.

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